

to diseases, and the slower the epidemic when it enters the polycyclic phase.

This behavior of the model indicates that it is sensitive to variation in r_s . Future development of the model must consider the effect of time-dependent factors on

variation in r_s so as to reflect variation of environment under which ShB epidemics develop. This suggests that the polycyclic nature of ShB must be considered a key characteristic of the disease for its management, and that measures taken in the course

of a cropping season should prove effective. It also indicates a comparatively high sensitivity of the model to variation in the aggregation parameter, and experiments are necessary for its estimation. ■

Use of CERES-Rice model to assess potential yield

G. S. L. H. V. Prasada Rao and N. Subash, Regional Agricultural Research Station (RARS), Pilicode 671353, Kasaragod District, Kerala, India

We conducted a field experiment at RARS, Pilicode ($12^{\circ} 12' N$; $75^{\circ} 10' E$; 2755 mm rainfall, 4.4 h of bright sunshine d^{-1}) to test the CERES-Rice model developed under the IBSNAT Project. Soils were well-drained sandy loam of lateritic origin with pH 5.5. The model was tested for five cropping seasons using different dates of transplanting during 1993 and 1994 kharif and 1992-93, 1993-94, and 1994-95 rabi. Popular varieties Jaya (120-125 d), Jyothi (110-125d), and Triveni (95-105d) were used.

The simulated grain yield through the CERES-Rice model was in good agreement with the observed yield during 1993 kharif while simulated grain yield was higher than that of the observed during 1994 kharif on all transplanting dates (Figs. a and b). Heavy rains during 1994 kharif brought floods. Incidence of gall midge and rice bug was also high at the time, leading to a high percentage of grain chaffing (see table).

The CERES-Rice model during rabi runs for a floodwater management scheme and takes into account bund height as well as floodwater maintained through irrigation at three different early stages of crop growth. The actual rabi crop at the field site was in a totally different condition from that mentioned previously. However, it should be noted that the CERES-Rice model simulated higher grain when run during rabi in all three test varieties on all transplanting dates.

This study reveals that the CERES-Rice model needs validation for rabi while it could very well be used during kharif to assess potential grain yields based on simple daily weather variables. ■

a. Actual and simulated grain yield ($t\ ha^{-1}$) of rice varieties on different dates of transplanting during 1993 kharif.

b. Actual and simulated grain yield ($t\ ha^{-1}$) of rice varieties on different dates of transplanting during 1994 kharif.

Percentage of grain chaffing of three test varieties during 1994 kharif on different dates of transplanting. Kerala, India, 1992-95.

Date of transplanting	Jaya		Jyothi		Triveni	
	Good grains (%)	Chaffing (%)	Good grains (%)	Chaffing (%)	Good grains (%)	Chaffing (%)
8 Jun	68.7	31.3	81.1	18.9	90.3	9.7
15 Jun	82.7	17.3	83.6	16.4	88.7	11.3
22 Jun	75.2	24.8	71.6	28.4	82.8	17.2
29 Jun	67.9	32.1	63.0	37.0	84.0	16.0
6 Jul	58.3	41.7	65.0	35.0	64.2	35.8
Av	70.6	29.4	72.9	27.1	82.0	18.0

Environment

Effect of contour hedgerow on runoff, soil loss, and upland rice production

C. R. Subudhi, P. C. Pradhan, and P. C. Senapati, Dry Land Agricultural Research Project (DLAP), Orissa University of Agriculture and Technology, Phulbani 7602001, Orissa, India

Most of the hilly areas in Orissa lose a lot of soil during the wet season. Soil loss and runoff, as affected by different contour hedgerows, were quantified and their effects on upland rice production determined.

The study was conducted at DLAP sites in Bhawanipatna in 1993 and in Phulbani in 1994. Soil at both sites is sandy loam with about 2% slope.

Rice (variety 9991 in 1993 and Heera in 1994) was dry-seeded in rows with 20-cm spacing along contours. Hedgerows separated rice terraces. The treatments (9 in 1993 and 7 in 1994) arranged in randomized complete block with three replications were the vegetation used to form the hedgerows (see table).

The hedgerows were planted with 1-yr-old grass seedlings (except for stylo where seeds were sown) 1 mo before the experiment. The distance between two hedgerows was 8 m. Plots were 25 m \times 3 m. Lengthwise, each plot comprised three terraces separated by two hedgerows.

Daily runoff was monitored using a multislit divisor. Runoff collected by one slit is fed into a drum installed at the end of the divisor. A sample of 250 ml was taken from each drum after thorough stirring and

Runoff, soil loss, and crop yield during 1993-94 cropping seasons.

Treatment	1993			1994			Mean yield (t ha ⁻¹)
	Runoff (mm)	Soil loss (t ha ⁻¹)	Crop yield (t ha ⁻¹)	Runoff (mm)	Soil loss (t ha ⁻¹)	Crop yield (t ha ⁻¹)	
T1 No hedgerows	184.1	3.5	1.2	204.0	10.4	1.3	1.3
T2 <i>Cynodon dactylon</i> hedgerow	154.9	3.0	1.0	172.2	5.5	1.7	1.4
T3 <i>Pennisetum purpureum</i> hedgerow	149.9	2.7	1.6	-	-	-	1.6
T4 <i>Vetiveria zizanioides</i> hedgerow	142.4	2.2	2.1	151.7	4.2	2.0	2.1
T5 <i>Eulaliopsis binata</i> hedgerow	150.7	2.4	1.4	162.4	4.8	1.9	1.7
T6 <i>Cymbopogon flexuosus</i> hedgerow ^a	151.8	2.6	1.9	-	-	-	1.9
T7 <i>Stylosanthes hamata</i> hedgerow	156.3	2.8	1.3	172.6	5.8	1.8	1.6
T8 Hybrid napier hedgerow ^b	155.2	3.1	1.6	-	-	-	1.6
T9 Fallow land	201.9	7.9	-	248.5	20.7	-	-
T10 Broadcasting of dry seed, no hedgerow ^c	-	-	-	235.7	11.1	1.0	1.01
Mean	160.8	3.3	1.5	191.0	8.9	1.5	1.6
LSD (0.01)			0.2			0.08	
SE (m)±			0.1			0.03	

^aTotal rainfall was 859 mm in 1993 and 1023 mm in 1994. ^bDone only in 1993. ^cDone only in 1994.

was evaporated to determine soil loss. The vetiver treatment (T4) produced the highest yield, having less runoff and less soil loss. Vetiver, with root penetration up to 1 m and consequently greater chances of survival than other grasses, was able to check the velocity of flow. Highest soil loss was observed in the fallow. Compared with leaving the land fallow (T9), 20% (1993) and 80% (1994) soil loss could be reduced by contour planting using vetiver. ■

Recommendations

Recommendations of the 3rd International Symposium on Hybrid Rice

The global requirement for rice by 2020 is expected to be around 800 million t compared with the current production of 520 million t. With shrinking resources—particularly arable land area, irrigation water, and energy—the only option left is to increase production. Increasing rice production by 300 million t during the next 25 yr will be a very challenging task. Of the possible genetic approaches to meet this challenge, hybrid rice technology is an immediate option since it has been a proven technology over the past 2 decades in China and is now showing commercial prospects in India.

The theme of the recent 3rd International Symposium on Hybrid Rice held in Hyderabad, India, 14-16 Nov 1996, was enhancement and sustenance of hybrid rice technology. The symposium was cosponsored by the Indian Council of Agricultural Research (ICAR), the United Nations Development Programme (UNDP), and IRRI. About 150 Indian delegates and 50 international delegates from 20 countries addressed various aspects and issues for improving the technology and making it available outside of China. These issues were deliberated in six sessions (current scenario, increasing breeding efficiency

and enhancing yield heterosis, sustainability of hybrid rice technology, tissue culture and molecular approaches in heterosis breeding, toward true-breeding hybrids, and status of development and adoption of hybrid rice technology in various countries) and a meeting of the International Task Force on Hybrid Rice. During the 3 d of sessions, the following major recommendations emerged.

Technology development

- Formation of a research network and effective collaboration with international agencies have been the main reasons for the remarkable success achieved in India. Use these approaches as models for similar achievements in other countries of South and Southeast Asia.
- Intensify efforts for development of hybrid rice technology in countries, such as India, Philippines, Vietnam, and Indonesia, where there is a demand for hybrid rice seeds and the capability to produce them.
- To meet consumer preference, emphasize improving milling, head rice recovery, and other quality characteristics.
- Especially emphasize incorporating resistance to major pests and diseases in the promising parental lines.

- To enhance the level of heterosis, the Chinese are successfully using two-line hybrids—photoperiod-sensitive gene male sterility (PGMS) and thermo-sensitive gene male sterility (TGMS)—and are developing hybrids through intersubspecific crossing of indicas and japonicas. Vigorously pursue these approaches in the tropics using indica/tropical japonica lines. Countries that grow japonica rices should be exploring the prospects of temperate japonica/tropical japonica hybrids.
- For full exploitation of rice hybrids, develop special management practices that promote efficient use of nitrogen, phosphorus, and other nutrients and water.
- Improve parental lines through the use of random mating populations—the private sector, particularly, should pursue this to minimize dependence on the public sector for the supply of improved parental lines.
- Develop rice hybrids adapted to different ecosystems—especially for the shallow lowlands, which are similar to the irrigated ecosystem.
- Intensify research to develop rice hybrids for the boro season (India, Bangladesh) and the spring season (Vietnam, Myanmar).